

Tapp (Water)

D. Arrildsen, N. Thielemann, E. Svendsen, T. Skou

DTU Process and Innovation, Technical University of Denmark

INTRODUCTION

If people in Denmark become aware of how much pollution and energy one half litre bottle of mineral-water consumes, it would lead to a change in the way we provide us self with water when we are on the go. In 2012, Denmark alone consumed 139,5 million litres of bottled mineral water, which led to a total emission of 25,1 million kilos co2 just for the water. In comparison the same amount of tap water would lead out 900 times less co2, 25 million kilos to be exact. We need water regularly throughout the day, but when we are on the go it is not always possible to provide ourselves whit fresh water unless we buy a bottle, which often is very expensive. Our goal is to provide fresh, clean and free tap water for the Danes, they only have to buy our bottle.

THEORY

We believe that if people can save money, they will automatically go for a greener alternative, especially if it is cheaper. With Tapp's new water solution where people buy their water bottle, use it for as long as they like and then deliver it back to be recycled, we can reduce our co2 emission by 105 gram every time the Tapp bottle is being reused. We have a theory that many people find it difficult to figure out how they can contribute in reducing co2 emission. With this in mind we are convinced that if people were made aware of how much pollution they just saved from getting out in the atmosphere every time they reused their bottle, it would lead to greater understanding of how they can contribute in lowering the co2 emission.

IDEA

The idea is to develop a service that will provide Denmark with fresh, clean and cold tap water for free, as long as they are using the Tapp water bottle. Automized water stands would be placed in minimarket around Denmark where it will read the integrated barcode underneath Tapp's water bottle, fill it with exactly 0,5 litre of fresh and cold tap water. When the bottle has been used for what the costumer finds appropriate he or she simply returns the old bottle to be re-cycled, buy a new Tapp water bottle for around 15 kroner and then fill it up at the stands. The reason why the bottle is empty is that we want to reduce co2 emission everywhere we can, therefore all of the bottle will be delivered empty so that the amount of energy for transport is being reduced and instead of large industrial refrigerators to cool a certain amount of bottle, we only need to cool a couple of litres inside the isolated water-stand.